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**MONETARY AND MACROPRUDENTIAL CONSTRAINTS ON MORTGAGE
 LENDING AND THEIR IMPACT ON HOUSING AFFORDABILITY
 IN THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION**

01.11.2025 . 2015–2024 -
 2015–2024 2025 -
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 2022 « » . , -

The article examines the impact of monetary, credit, and macroprudential constraints in mortgage lending on housing affordability in the Russian Federation over 2015–2024, incorporating assessment indicators as of November 1, 2025. Mortgage-based housing affordability is considered a key indicator of socio-economic resilience and of the realization of citizens' constitutional right to housing. Using evidence for 2015–2024 and assessment data for 2025, the study analyzes the mortgage market's shift from an accommodative monetary policy regime toward a configuration combining an elevated key policy rate, tighter macroprudential add-ons, and more granular regulatory requirements for borrowers. Housing affordability is interpreted as an integrated outcome of a set of regulatory eligibility filters, including the key policy rate and its transmission into mortgage rates; borrower-level requirements related to the debt burden indicator and down payment; caps on the share of higher-risk loans; and the program and legal parameters of state support.

Program-related and banking constraints are treated as derivatives of monetary and macroprudential policy decisions formalized in the regulatory acts of the Bank of Russia and the Government of the Russian Federation. The methodological framework includes statistical analysis of interest rates, housing prices, and household incomes; regulatory and legal analysis of decisions adopted by the Bank of Russia and the Government; macroeconomic modeling of affordability metrics (payment burden, a payment-based affordability index, and an index of relative housing inaccessibility); and an author-developed "constraint ladder" model supplemented by a constraints matrix and a system of traffic-light threshold indicators. The results indicate that after 2022, amid tighter macroprudential add-ons and stricter regulation of the debt burden indicator, mortgages increasingly lose the characteristics of a mass-market product and evolve into a selective access mechanism for limited household groups, thereby strengthening differentiation by income level, regional conditions, and borrowers' risk profiles. The practical contribution of the study is the development of an approach to assess how regulatory decisions affect housing affordability and the substantiation of directions for adjusting mortgage policy, taking into account debt-burden risks and the need to preserve the social function of mortgage lending.

Keywords: housing affordability; mortgage housing finance; monetary policy; macroprudential regulation; key policy rate; debt service-to-income ratio; government support programmes; mortgage selectivity; threshold indicators of affordability; social function of mortgage lending.

2021–2022

01.11.2025 2015-2024
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• . . . [9, .70-81] -

• . . . ; [10, .117-128] -

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2025 . . . 2022- -

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• . . . [12, .107-116] « -

• . . . [13, .86-97] -

• . . . [14], -

• . . . [15, .253-257] « » -

• . . . [16, .68-70], -

• . . . [17, .2095-2103] -

16.07.1998 102- « ((40))».
 ()», 10.07.2002 86- «

1 2015–2025

I. *

	()		
2015–2020	4,25 %		
2021	8,50 %		
2022	20 % 7,50 %		
2023–2024	16–21 %		
2025 (- 01.11.2025)	16,50 %		

* [18; 19]

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2015–2020 2015–2024 2025
 4,25
 2021 8,5
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2022

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* [20; 21; 25]

	() , %	%	1 .	50 . . ,	(80 %),	'	/	
2015	11,00	12,5	59 352	2 967 600	2 374 080	26 973	34 030	0,79
2016	10,00	12,5	60 542	3 027 100	2 421 680	27 514	36 709	0,75
2017	7,75	10,6	58 900	2 945 000	2 356 000	23 680	39 144	0,60
2018	7,75	9,9	60 180	3 009 000	2 407 200	23 071	43 445	0,53
2019	6,25	9,9	60 050	3 002 500	2 402 000	23 021	47 867	0,48
2020	4,25	7,4	69 214	3 460 700	2 768 560	22 134	51 352	0,43
2021	8,50	8,3	81 645	4 082 300	3 265 840	27 929	56 545	0,49
2022	7,50	9,6	104 737	5 236 850	4 189 480	39 325	65 338	0,60
2023	16,00	8,2	113 216	5 660 800	4 528 640	38 445	74 854	0,51
2024	21,00	8,7	142 984	7 149 200	5 719 360	50 360	87 952	0,57

* [18; 19; 20; 21; 22; 23; 24; 25; 26]

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0,43,
43
2015 2016
0,79 0,75,
0,48 2019
0,43 2020
2023–2024
16–21
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8,2–8,7

5. 2015–2024 .*

2015–2021 ~7–8 % 0,43–0,49;

2022–2024 8,2–9,6 % ; 0,60; 0,51–

2022 2022 5

	, %		
2015–2021	~7–8 %	0,43–0,49;	
2022–2024	8,2–9,6 %	; 0,60;	0,51–

* [25; 26; 27; 28; 29]

7.

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-	≤ 10 %	10-14 %	> 14 %	-
-	≤ 10 %	10-14 %	> 14 %	14 %
-	≤ 40 %	40-50 %	> 50 %	50 %
()	≤ 4 %	4-8 %	> 8 %	-
()	≥ 6 %	3-6 %	< 3 %	-
	≥ 40 %	20-40 %	< 20 %	-
	≥ 0 %	-5-0 %	< -5 %	.

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7

2015-2024

2017-2020
2022-2024

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9. « » *

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2022–2025

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